

Holistic approach of yoga in promoting health and well-being in modern life

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Abstracts:

In today's fast-paced world, stress and anxiety have become a recurring factor in everyone's life. Modern life patterns, inactivity and unhealthy food habits affect our health in different aspects physically, psychologically, and socially. To recover from the stress, it is very essential to find inner peace and maintain physical as well as mental wellness. There is a need for increasing people awareness about the effect of modern life to control the effects of the patterns of life. Promoting healthy lifestyle involves proper eating, developing positive habits, engaging in moral and physical activity, and better way of communicating and socializing in the community. All this can only be achieved by regularly practicing yoga. The purpose of Yoga is the attainment of physical, mental and spiritual harmony . Health is the main goal of everyone and therefore without spending a lot of money by practicing Yoga, one can achieve good health and mind. Therefore, this paper discusses the importance and benefit of Yoga in modern life to encourage the reader to practice Yoga to maintain physical, mental, social and spiritual health.

Keywords: Yoga, Modern Life, physical and mental Health.

Introduction

Before discussing the importance of Yoga in modern lifestyles it is essential to discuss the problems and issues associated with modern life. It is clear that modern lifestyles are making life easier for men in today's world. Nobody can deny the usefulness and benefits of modernization on our daily life, especially on how much it

makes life of humans easier. However, the different modern lifestyle is something that is quiet unhealthy and raises the possibility of a number of social, psychological, and physical issues. Modern life style becomes more and more an important factor influencing health state of most developed countries. For example, the widespread use of technology machines, fast foods, sophisticated transportation, and the use of the computer including internet and video games that is being used by almost every member of the family. Moreover, the modern lifestyle is characterised by drug, alcohol consumption, smoking, fast food, unhealthy diet, excessive use of technologies and substance abuse. These are all prevalent in our society which is leading to various problems for the people living in it. People in the modern world are more susceptible to various illnesses, disabilities, and even death due to their unhealthy lifestyle choices. Modern lifestyle intensifies the risk of fatness or obesity, diabetes, heart diseases, and cancers. The modern lifestyle, which puts people under constant stress, depression, hypertension, and hyperlipidaemia could severely damage major organs and lead to heart attacks, kidney disease and dementia. Many respiratory and skin conditions are also exacerbated by pollution from transportation and high-tech machinery. Furthermore, it has been noted that children experience excessive stress in their environment, which includes the playground, home, and school. Social isolation is a result of using computers and the internet for extended periods of time. They have numerous issues, including emotional, mental, and physical ones, as a result of this stress. When these health hazards create problems for long, they lead to psychosomatic diseases and social unrest. The root cause of all these issues is an imbalance in our spiritual, mental, and physical selves. They have a close connection to a materialistic lifestyle. Our suffering is mostly caused by two things: attachment and unending ambition.

Therefore, there is a need to increase awareness among the people to control their lifestyle by promoting proper physical activities to socializing and communicate in society. All this can only be achieved by regularly practicing yoga. The practice of *Yoga* brings change in all aspects. Yoga is a natural therapy that helps us achieve mental relaxation by collaborating with our body, mind, and soul. Yoga will decrease the risk

of getting deadly diseases that result from an uneven lifestyle. In today's fast-paced world, stress and anxiety have become a constant factor in everyone's life. To recover from the stress, it is very important to find inner peace and maintain physical as well as mental wellness. Yoga is the oldest and most traditional method for achieving this. The importance of *yoga* in modern life can be divided into physical, mental and spiritual benefits. Yoga is an art that originated in India many years ago, yoga is now considered one of the best forms of exercise. People are aware of yoga's health benefits, which include improved mental clarity, a rejuvenated spirit, and a balanced lifestyle. Yoga is incredibly safe and accessible to all ages, with both adults and children benefiting from its many advantages. Yoga reinforces several components of mental health. It may act as a good tool to promote mental well-being and prevent mental illness. Interestingly, research on yoga has demonstrated its immediate psychological benefits, including a reduction in stress and anxiety as well as an increase in emotions and social well-being.

Thus, Yoga helps “reduce stress, maintain and improve our health and well-being, and build more harmonious and fulfilling relationships.

Methodology

This study is descriptive in nature and the data have been collected from research articles and research papers, various journals, reference books web resources, etc.

Discussion:

Concept of Yoga

Yoga is an ancient art which was originated in India around six thousand years ago. The Rig Vedas is the earliest known source of its documentation. Yoga comprises of physical, mental and spiritual practises and promotes self-healing. The word ‘yoga’ is derived from the Sanskrit word ‘yuj’ meaning to join, to yoke, and to unite. A union with the universe can be attained as well along with a proper understanding and appreciation of the world one lives in. In the earlier days, the followers of Hinduism, Buddhism, and Jainism practiced it. Since then, yoga has been practiced by individuals

all over the world to decompress and maintain physical fitness. Yoga is a philosophy or an art of living that combines a physical, spiritual, and mental path. It makes it possible to reach quiet and access one's inner awareness. Yoga is a physical discipline that focuses on bringing the body, mind, and soul into balance. Regular practice of yoga brings positive changes in the practitioner – strong muscles, flexibility, patience and good health. Thus, Yoga is a worldwide phenomenon and is widely practised in the modern world for its far-reaching properties. As Bhagavad Gita puts it, “yoga is the journey of the self, to the self, through the self.” Yoga combines strength and flexibility exercises along with relaxation and meditation.

The main aim of Yoga is the attainment of the physical, mental and spiritual health. According to Patanjali, yoga consists of eight steps or limbs, which are all equally significant and are interconnected as parts of a whole. The purpose of these eight limbs is discriminative enlightenment or self-realization. But here the emphasis will be on health benefits. The eight steps or limbs of yoga are as follows:

- Yamas- Codes of restraint, abstinences, self-regulations
- Niyamas- cleanliness, contentment, mortification, study and worship of God.
- Asanas- Physical postures or exercises
- Pranayama: Expansion of breath and prana, regulation, control
- Pratyahara- Withdrawal of the senses, bringing inward
- Dharana- Concentration of the mind
- Dhyana- Meditation
- Samadhi: Deep absorption, meditation in its higher state, the state of perfected concentration

Yoga for healthy lifestyle

Today, the importance of *Yoga* is growing all over the world. Incorporating yoga into daily life can lead to positive lifestyle changes . This ancient science takes a holistic approach to health, believing that the body, mind, and spirit are all interconnected. It is an ancient system of self-development and natural process of evolution of human

beings. Even under tough situations, yoga is said to provide optimal physical, mental, and social wellbeing. The word "yoga" has a significant influence on people's lives these days. Busy schedules lead to an increase in individualism and loneliness. In other words, lives in an urban modern society are more complex and often filled with tensions due to more work pressures and financial pressures. As consequence, many people experience stressful lives and have hectic schedules which characterize an urban modern lifestyle. Yoga is a gift, that is given to us by our ancestors, sages to awaken the latent abilities. Regular practice of yoga can also improve sleep quality and boost energy levels, enhancing overall productivity and quality of life and the practice of dhyana will help us to improve our focus or concentration which is the most needed for an individual in the modern life.

It plays a significant role in reducing the emotional, stressful baggage and is also helpful in curing behavioural disorder, nervous breakdown, maniac depression. Even during the COVID-19 pandemic, when there were few opportunities for social and physical interaction and it seemed like we were stuck in a never-ending cycle, yoga acted as a channel to increase our inner strength and personal power. Thus, the ultimate purpose of yoga is the attainment of human growth.

Benefits of Yoga

Yoga has far-reaching benefits to achieving perfect harmony in one's life, from managing physical, mental, spiritual and social health. Yoga is said to have benefits when practised from a young age. Moreover, yoga helps to develop spiritual progress by balancing the mind and soul. From controlling senses to harmonising inner energy, yoga can develop mindfulness and eradicate stress and anxiety. Numerous workshops are held and now there are even professional yogis who teach this ancient practice to people so they can learn about it.

Yoga is considered to be an alternate therapy to medication and treatment. Hatha yoga, shavasana, and pranayams are a few exercises that are very popular in yoga. Yoga is an art which connects our body, mind and soul together and makes us strong and peaceful. Yoga has numerous benefits if we look at it closely. In addition, when we

practice several asanas and postures, it strengthens our body and gives us a feeling of well-being and healthiness. By practicing yoga regularly, people are being benefited on the following points:

Physical health

Healthy – A healthy individual is more productive and can accomplish more than an unhealthy one. Life nowadays is very stressful and there is lot of pollution around us. This is the root cause of many health problems. Doing yoga for just 10 to 20 minutes a day can help us get our health back. A healthier life is a better life.

Activeness – People nowadays feel lazy, tired or sleepy. Due to which they miss out most of the fun in life and are not able to complete their work correctly. By practicing yoga regularly, we may aware of the things happening around us and it also helps us to complete our work more efficiently and quickly.

Flexibility – Regular practice of yoga asanas encourages body movement in different directions, assisting in opening that reduces stiffness, joint pains, increases joint mobility, and releases pent-up emotions leading to strength and flexibility.

Increase Blood Flow – Yoga helps make our heart healthy and makes it work more efficiently by increasing blood flow in our body and veins. Exercises like headstands will help us to pump blood from the lower part of the body to back to our heart.

Increase metabolism – Practising yoga daily will help us to retain the energy of our body by keeping it fit. It helps to improve the metabolic system of the body.

Help us to sleep better – Stress, workload, and anxiety will disrupt our sleeping pattern. The best yoga asana that will reduce our anxiety, stress, and creates a perfect routine for sleep. It relaxed and calm body gets more peaceful and deep sleep

Keep you away from serious diseases – Daily yoga exercise will help us to get the best immune system and increase the power to fight against diseases

Controls cholesterol and blood sugar – With the changes in lifestyle and eating habits, most people are suffering from diabetes and cholesterol. In this case, the practice of yoga asanas and pranayama will help us in controlling blood sugar and lower bad cholesterol, overweight and obesity.

Mental health:

Aside from the physical benefits, one of the best benefits of yoga is how it helps a person manage mental health. It might be a useful tool for preventing mental disease and promoting mental health. Stress is common these days and is known to have detrimental effects on one's body and mind. Due to stress people develop serious problems like sleeping disorder, neck pain, back pain, headaches, rapid heart rate, anxiety, depression, dissatisfaction, anger, insomnia and inability to concentrate. Yoga is known to be really effective in curing these kinds of problems over a period of time. Through breathing exercises and meditation, it helps people manage stress and enhances their mental health. Regular practice creates mental clarity and calmness thereby relaxing the mind. Some of the mental benefits of yoga are as follows:

Inner Peace – Yoga helps achieve inner peace and fight against stress and other problems. A person who practices yoga gains more joy and serenity in his life, which boosts his confidence.

Power to Concentrate – We can achieve a higher level of concentration through yoga and also learn how to steady our emotions. Yoga helps our body to calm down and relax which means there is less stress and one can concentrate and focus quickly on his work. Those who have survived modern life understand the value of focus because they are frequently juggling multiple responsibilities. One effective technique for improving focus is meditation. That is why children and teenagers are encouraged to do yoga because it helps them concentrate better on their studies.

Developing intelligence and mental balance in students - Furthermore, yoga helps in sharpening our mind and improving our intelligence. Yoga and meditation not only benefit adult or elderly people, but it is very helpful to students as well. If students

regularly practice meditating under proper guidance, they will be benefited in numerous ways. It may help to increase in IQ level, lower stress, get over depression, developing confidence and thereby keep students happy and relax.

Discipline and Mindfulness in Life – Yoga can foster discipline and self-care habits, promoting a healthier lifestyle. By implementing the Yamas and Niyamas written in the Yoga Sutras of Patanjali, we invite more discipline and mindfulness into our living. The five Yamas and Niyamas are the ethical codes of living a virtuous life. Yoga is considered as main source of fostering values among young minds to get over from bad addiction, habits and immoralities.

Conclusion

We can draw the conclusion that living in the modern world is complicated and stressful. The majority of issues in the present day are caused by a poor lifestyle. The advancement of technology has created a competitive environment for modern man. The way people live today has completely changed, particularly in urban industrial societies. This includes eating habits, work styles, and family structures. We have entirely modified our lives to conform to this modern tradition, and consequently we have forgotten the moral ideals of life and peace, as well as many other fundamental components of our lives. People who lead this lifestyle experience stress, which can result in a variety of illnesses. Therefore, practicing yoga is significant in controlling health problems resulted from modern life situation. Yoga is a holistic approach that embodies the union of our physical, mental, social and spiritual health. It can foster discipline and self-care habits, promoting a healthier lifestyle. Yoga is rightly called 'A science to live in harmony with self and the world' – it is not only for keeping our body fit but also helps us to keep our mind and soul active. The practice unites the body, mind, and soul together and enables us to be happy, peaceful, and content by changing our attitudes, behavior, and outlook towards life. Moreover, it connects us to nature like never before and enhances our social well-being. Throughout the COVID-19 response, yoga has helped hundreds of millions of people from all countries and cultures stay healthy and well, consistent with the conviction – expressed in WHO's constitution –

that health is not merely the absence of disease or infirmity, but rather a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being. In addition, we can develop self-discipline and self-awareness and lead a healthy and problem free life from yoga if practiced regularly. 21st of June is celebrated as International Day of Yoga where people are made aware of the benefits of yoga. Yoga is a great gift to mankind which helps us keep better and maintain our health.

In short, we have understood the several benefits of yoga. Everyone must practice it to keep their health maintained and also benefit from it. It is the key to living a long and healthy life without utilizing any artificial methods, such as medications or other shortcuts of any kind.

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